

APPENDIX B: LESSONS LEARNED ON STEPS TO IMPLEMENT GROUND BASED REMOTE SENSING (GBRS) NETWORK FROM START

The trigger

Types of triggers:

- sources of external knowledge transfer about the ground based remote sensing (GBRS) field and applications:
 - conferences, working groups of official international bodies, neighbouring countries cooperation, technical and meteorological expos, private environmental companies
- One person's know-how and former experiences (trans-generational transfer of knowledge and experiences)
- Common recognition from a user or a group of users for the need to use ground based remote sensing data after being faced with specific anthropogenic or atmospheric events that influenced their operational work

Project feasibility meetings

Making management and potential cooperating departments understand that ground based remote sensing network represents a leap forward when the network will be set up and the end user products will be available.

Discussing with involved parties: national agency or company management, cooperating departments, about:

- how ground based remote sensing field fits into the agency's or company's current organisational structure and vision (long term plans)
- potential stakeholders and end users
- size and type of the network:
 - smaller local or bigger national network
 - heterogeneous or homogenous sensor types and technology
- material and human resources (man power) for implementation and operational phase

Steps to consider

STEP	Actions	Output	Important
Professional community outreach and technology research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Contact many different Agencies, Companies and Institutes ● Contact or check the web pages of international organisations (WMO, EUMETNET, COST, ISO ...) ● Search the web using keywords relevant to the topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge of the state of ground based remote sensing (GBRS) technology and applications from research to operational level ● Basic Know-how of how different GBRS sensors work and are being used with their pros/cons 	<p>Start to establish new contacts with potential end users and management.</p> <p>Recursively discuss the GBRS field pros with the potential users. Gradually you will understand end user needs and they will understand what GBRS field can offer.</p> <p>Repeat the cycle and locate new users.</p>

STEP	Actions	Output	Important
		<p>for research or operational usage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instrument technical specifications like resolution, range and uncertainty and existing known user needs 	
<p>Market research</p>	<p>Contact products suppliers (companies), providing them with your knowledge of the field. Present your intended application and size of the network and the structure of your central IT infrastructure (virtual, physical, linux, windows, server, desktop). Use structured and concrete questions about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Measured parameters ● Configuration parameters ● Range ● Resolution ● Uncertainty ● Power supply ● Environmental sensitivity ● Internal processing unit ● Data formats ● Communication physical link and protocols ● Wireless communication options ● Possibility of data quality control ● Calibration procedures ● Maintenance protocols ● Spare parts and long term availability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How the market functions and the size of the market ● Which company is more opened to discussion and flexible when it comes to user demands ● Which company has a good know-how on the subject ● Products technical specifications like resolution, range and uncertainty 	<p>You have at this stage some technical and operational knowledge from the community that you can use when addressing the market companies.</p>

STEP	Actions	Output	Important
Final market and community research report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare the report • Present the report • Evaluate the report according to end user needs, management and budget 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A reached decision on what to buy and how to proceed with the procurement and implementation 	Re-evaluate potential stakeholders and end users.
Procurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare the procurement documents based on your needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement documentation with technical specifications according to your application needs 	Prepare good technical specifications based on the knowledge and experiences acquired during the former steps.
Network implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate sensor set-up with cooperating bodies (neighbouring departments responsible for existing networks, IT, ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinated implementation of the new sensors with low level data flow from sensors to company servers • End user and cooperating departments coordination 	Coordinate the locations of the sensors with end user needs if possible.
Data flow, user products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design a data flow scheme for each type of sensor from data retrieval to end products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational data flow scheme 	End products can change or adapt with time.
Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare standard operating procedures (SoP) for each sensor • Organise regular data and sensor inspections 	SoP for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular maintenance • Calibration • Troubleshooting 	Source of information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User guides • International community
Management and End Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide the management with success stories from the new network • Re-evaluate end user group and reach out to potential new users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success stories presentations for management to strengthen the position of the new GBRS field in the 	Management is the one that provides funds and you have to build trust in professional field of GBRS. List of end users provides strong arguments for the importance of GBRS field.

STEP	Actions	Output	Important
		operational monitoring field <ul style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="810 219 1027 358">● Presentations and talks for reaching out to new users	